

Research article**Management of Tennis Elbow or *Snayugata Vata* Affecting *Koorpara Sandhi*
- A Case Report**

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Abstract -

Pain is a common problem that disrupts our daily lives. Snayugata Vata affecting Koorpara sandhi, popularly known as Tennis elbow, or pain in the elbow joint, is a prime example. Effective treatment can significantly reduce pain and help people resume their normal activities.

While Tennis Elbow gets its name from the sport, it's not just athletes who get it. Computer operators, teachers, and housewives can also develop this condition.

A 35-year-old male, computer operator by profession, came to the hospital, in the outpatient department, with a complaint of severe pain in the right elbow and was unable to perform his duties in the office. He was given tablets of Trayodashang Guggulu (Ayurvedic preparation made of 13 herbs with Cow's ghee) 500mg, 2 tablets twice a day orally and Nirgundipatra Upanaha (Local application of Nirgundipatra, Saindhav lavana and Til oil) daily once before bedtime for a period of 21 days. Evaluation was noted every week for 4 weeks.

The subject showed a decrease in pain and improvement in performing his daily activities on the computer after 28 days of treatment. This painless, long-lasting, and easy-to-use Ayurvedic treatment could benefit many people suffering from Tennis Elbow or Snayugata Vata affecting Koorpara sandhi.

Keywords: *Snayugata Vata, Tennis Elbow, Trayodashang Guggulu, Nirgundipatra, Upanaha, Pain-in-elbow.*

1. Introduction

Pain is a very common reason people see doctors. It disrupts the daily lives of people and Tennis Elbow or *Snayugata Vata* affecting *Koorpara Sandhi* is a prime example.

Tennis elbow causes pain in the forearm due to inflammation or small tears in the tendons. It's often caused by repetitive motions from work, sports, or even housework. Symptoms include pain, stiffness, limited movement, tenderness, and weak grip.

Its incidence is 1 to 3% in the population [1] and it is most common between ages 30 and 60, although it can strike anyone [2].

While tennis elbow can improve on its own within 6 months to 2 years, treatment can speed up recovery and get you back to your activities faster.

Because the symptoms are similar, Tennis Elbow can be compared to *Snayugata Vata* affecting *Koorpara Sandhi* in Ayurveda. This condition is caused by an imbalance in *Vata dosha*. Ayurvedic treatment typically involves a topical poultice or *Upanaha* made with *Vitex Negundo* leaves or *Nirgundipatra* and oral tablets like *Trayodashang Guggulu*.

Figure 1: Pathogenesis of Arthritis

Case Report

A 35-year-old male, came with complaint of pain in right elbow and was unable to perform his duties in office, particularly work on computer. He had pain since last one month and he felt better with some pain killers. But the pain aggravated as soon as he stopped taking the tablets. The pain was in and around the right elbow and was pricking in nature.

- **History of present illness**

The patient was normal and doing computer work for 12 years, before the pain started one month back. The pain in right elbow started after he worked on computer continuously for more than 8 hours. He had to work in this pattern frequently and he used to take some pain killers for the same. He used to feel better for a day or two but then the pain would reappear. The patient did not get complete relief and hence he came to *Kayachikitsa* (Medicine) Department, of our hospital.

Figure 1: Neuropathy Pathogenesis

- **Past history**

There was no history of fall or any injury to hand. There was no history of Tuberculosis, Diabetes mellitus, Hypertension, or any kind of Surgery performed. No chronic illness reported.

- **Family history**

No evidence of any such disease in the family.

- **Physical examination**

Examination of affected part – No obvious swelling over the right elbow was observed.

Movements restricted - Cozens Test and Mill’s Manoeuvres test is positive [3]. Tenderness is mildly positive.

Nadi or Pulse: *Pittaj nadi*, 84/min, regular

Prakṛti (body constitution) - *Vata-pittaja*

Jihwa (Tongue) – *Nirama* (uncoated)

Agni bala (Digestive power) – *madhyam* (medium)

Sharir bala (physique) - *uttam* (good)

Sara (Composition) – *madhyam* (medium).

Body temperature: 98.2° F

Blood pressure: 122/76 mmHg

Respiratory rate: 21/min.

No pallor, no icterus

No Bilateral pedal oedema

Systematic examination –

C.V.S. – Normal, No abnormal sound

Respiratory System -Bilateral Air Entry

C.N.S. - Conscious and oriented

P/A - Soft. Liver, Spleen – not palpable

Figure 3: Arthritis Disease Mechanism

- **Investigation**

Plain X-ray Rt. Elbow AP & Lateral view showed no abnormality.

2. Material and Methods

Tablets of *Trayodashang Guggulu* [4] were given orally and *Nirgundipatra* (Leaves of *Vitex negundo*) [5] *Upanaha* (poultice) [6] was given as local application.

Trayodashang Guggulu is a traditional Ayurvedic herbal formulation used in tablet form to manage pain. It is a mixture of 13 herbs – *Aabha* (*Acacia Arabica*), *Ajawayan* (*Carum copticum*), *Ashwgandha* (*Withania somnifera*), *Gokshur* (*Tribulus terrestris*), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cardifolia*), *Hapusha* (*Juniperus communis*), *Karchoor* (*Curcuma zedoria*), *Rasna* (*Pluchea lanceolata*), *Shatapushpa* (*Foeniculum vulgare*), *Shatavari* (*Asparagus racemosus*), *Shunthi* (*Zingiber officinale*), *Vrudhadaruk* (*Ipomoea Petaloidea/biloba*), including *Guggulu* processed in Cow Ghee [7]. Tablets of 500mg were prepared. Two tablets twice daily were given with lukewarm water.

Nirgundi patra or crushed fresh leaves, *Saindhav lavana* (Rock salt) and *Til taila* (Sesame oil) were mixed in equal quantity and cooked to form a regular mixture. Warm application was then applied, about 40 degrees centigrade temperature, around the lateral epicondylar region of elbow. That part is then covered with the crepe bandage. The process was done in the evening hours, before bed time (*Vata kala*) and kept overnight.

Figure 1: Application of Nirgundipatra Upanaha

Figure 2: Nirgundipatra Upanaha secured with crepe bandage

3. Criteria for Assessment:

The total improvement in the patient was assessed based on the pain relief he got in the signs and symptoms of the disease. The objective and subjective parameters were as follows –

- A. Objective parameter - Hand Grip Dynamometer was used to assess the hand grip strength.
- B. Subjective parameters – The Following parameters were used to assess: Pain (*Shoola*), Functional disability (*Stambha*), Pricking sensation (*Toda*), Radiation of pain (*Sanchari Vedana*) and Tenderness or *Pidanasahatwa*.

4. Results

The result was drawn on the basis of objective and subjective criteria. The result was as per the following table: Table No :1

• Discussion

Snayugata Vata of *Koorpara Sandhi* can be very well compared with Tennis elbow. The *Vata* after vitiation, gets lodged in *Snayu* or fibrous structure of *Koorpara Sandhi* or lateral side of elbow joint, it is then labelled as *Snayugata Vata* affecting *Koorpara Sandhi* [8].

Criteria of Assessment	Sign-Symptoms	Day 0	Day 7	Day 14	Day 21	Day 28
Objective	Hand Grip Strength Evaluation in kgs	4 kg	6 kg	10 kg	15 kg	20 kg
Subjective	Pain or <i>Shoola</i>	10	8	6	3	1
Questions were asked to understand the level of difficulty and rating was done on a scale of 0 to 10. No pain is 0 and painful or difficult condition is 10	Functional disability or <i>Stambh</i>	9	7	4	2	0
	Pricking sensation or <i>Toda</i>	10	8	5	2	0
	Radiation of pain or <i>Sanchari Vedana</i>	9	7	5	3	1
	Tenderness or <i>Pidasahatwa</i>	8	6	4	2	1

Various factors responsible for Vata vitiation or Nidan, like improper diet (*aharaj*) and lifestyle habits (*viharaj* – working continuously for long hours) can lead to *Vata dosha* imbalance or *Vata prakopa* in the body [9]. The vitiated *Vata dosha* settles in the tendons (*snayu*) near the elbow joint (*koorpara sandhi*). This imbalance manifests as pain (*shoola*), stiffness or functional disability (*Stambha*), pricking sensation (*Toda*), etc. in the affected area [10].

Snayugata Vata is a disease developed with the vitiation of Vata and Vata dosha along with other nidana factors create Vata prakopa and an increase in khara, ruksha and shita guna of the tendon.

Due to increase in the kharatwa property, the snayu becomes brittle and vulnerable to tears. The collagen loses its structure due to the constant force applied to the tendon for a prolonged period. This unstructured collagen indicates that the collagen no longer has the strength to perform its functions suggesting dhatu kshaya [19]. This dhatu kshaya makes the tendon unable to bear the weight, resulting in reduced grip strength.

Since *Snayugata Vata* is an illness covered under *Vatavyadhi*, *Vatahara* course of treatment is recommended [11]. The treatments include *Snehana* or Oelevation, *Upanaha* or Poulitice, *Agnikarma* or Cauterization, *Bandhana* or Bandaging, and *Unmardana* or massage besides oral drugs [12].

Tennis elbow, also called as Lateral epicondylitis, is a condition that causes pain in the forearm. This pain can be caused by inflammation or tiny tears in the tendons that connect the forearm muscles to the elbow bone. These tears are often caused by repetitive motions during sports, work, or even everyday activities.

The main symptoms of tennis elbow include pain, trouble moving your elbow, stiffness, tenderness, and a weak grip. People who are at risk for tennis elbow include not only the Tennis players but also computer users, surgeons, musicians who play string instruments, and people who do a lot of housework.

Conventional Treatment show drawbacks like adverse effects on the body hence, a complete or long-lasting solution is needed.

- **Discussion on treatment**

Trayodashang Guggulu possess essential properties like *Vata Shamana* (Pacification of *Vata dosha*), *Sandhibalyakara* (gives strength to joints) and *Vedanashamak* (pain reliever) along with other properties. The contents in *Trayodashang Guggulu* are *Balya* (strength giver), *Rasayana* (rejuvenator) and provide strength to *Dhatu*. *Guggulu* is also used in and it is known to act as a *Rasayana* (rejuvenator) and in all types of *Vata* disorders or diseases. *Guggulu* has proven analgesic, anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant properties [13].

Nirgundipatra Upanaha or *Nirgundipatra* poultice is a form of *Svedana*, described in Ayurvedic texts (sudation therapy). As per the studies published, the lipid medium helps in the penetration of the drug molecule and it is the most suitable media for penetration via stratum corneum [14]. Taking this into consideration, it is assumed that the oil used in preparation of *Nirgundipatra upanaha*, acts as a lipoidal medium and penetration of the drug molecules of *Nirgundi* is possible. An immediate anti-inflammatory effect is seen [15].

As these drugs address every aspect of pathogenesis of *Snayugata Vata* affecting *Koorpara Sandhi* also termed as Tennis elbow, the above-mentioned regimen was chosen for the study.

- **Conclusion**

This case study shows that Tennis Elbow or *Snayugata Vata* affecting *Koorpara Sandhi* can be successfully managed with Ayurvedic intervention. It is a cost-effective, easy to perform procedure, non-invasive treatment and the relief in pain is forever or for very long time. In addition to Tennis players, people from other professions too suffer from this and need treatment to continue their regular activities or routine practise in various sports or music, without pain. It is supportive for further research in pains, Reiter syndrome and other autoimmune dermatological disorders.

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